

Overview of the Contribution of Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services to the Development of Literacy Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Literacy is an indispensable foundation that enables young people and adults to engage in learning opportunities at all stages of the learning. It has also been found as a means of building people's capabilities to cope with the evolving challenges and complexities of life economy culture and society. History of literacy development in Nigeria cannot be complete without the Assessment and Contribution of Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) in making adult be included in National policy in Education. This conclusion was made possible with the contribution of the professionals in the field. The joint contribution between Academia and professional created earlier involvement of that stakeholders like United Nations Literacy Decade UNLD, Literacy Initiative for Empowerment LIFE/LAMP, and NCML, World Bank. The sustainability of literacy development was short lived because of divorce of interest between the academia who constitutes majority of members Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services NOGALSS and professional in the field of adult education leading to the formation of Nigeria National Council for Adult Education NNCAE.

Keywords: Assessment, Contribution, NOGALSS, Development Literacy Education, Nigerian.

Introduction

Literacy is an indispensable foundation that enables young people and adult to engage in learning opportunities at all stages of the learning continuum. The right literacy is an inherent part of the right to education. It is a prerequisite for the development of personal, social economic and political empowerment. Literacy is an essential means of building people's capabilities to cope with the evolving challenges and complexities of life culture, economy and society United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO] (2009). Literacy has been defined in different ways by scholars and academic and professional bodies in the field of adult education. Rogers in Aderinoye (2004) defined literacy as the degree to which an individual possesses mastery over symbols in their written form, or is able to encode the symbols which may be letters or numbers. Aderinoye (2004) and Indabawa (1995) also submitted the definition of literacy as an exercise affected by times, place and culture. The definition by Indabawa (1995) of literacy as the ability to encode and decode with a view to community information, skills, meaning and ideas for the facilitation of day to day living. That also informed the new definition of literacy by the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO as a dynamic concept formerly understood as just reading writing and basic numeracy; the concept has been enlarged to encompass a whole range of more complex and a diverse skill and understanding United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) 2006 in Nigeria National Council for Adult Education NNCAE 2008 & 198).

Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) was established in 1993 by national mass education commission, Abuja as an umbrella body for all NGOs PVOs and individuals that are involved in mass literacy delivery in Nigeria. It was established to complement government efforts in the provision of functional mass literacy and basic education at all levels. Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) was set up by NGOs that are fully or partly working on adult literacy and non-formal education Sub-sector government efforts in the delivery of programmes. NOGALSS collaborate with ministries Department and Agencies (MDAS) such as National Commission for Mass Literacy, Adult and Non-Formal Education NMEC and SAMS, development partners such as United Nations Literacy Decade UNLD, Literacy Initiative for Empowerment LIFE, LAMP, United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund UNICEF, United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO and other Non- Government Organizations NGOs like Civil Society Action Coalition on Education for All CSACEFA and Non-Government Association for Literacy Support Services NOGALSS, Nigeria National Council for Adult Education NNCAE to fight the menace of illiteracy in the country (NOGALSS)208

Literacy Education has a special role in the process of community development and growth this is because education service serves as a vehicle that set up other economic process in to motion, Biallo (2002), he stressed further that, an education and literate society serve as a pivot or better still an orbit upon which the development of the kinds resolves. The acquisitions of literacy avails the recipient the opportunity for Personal development and enable him or her to become a matured and responsible citizen to his country.

Literacy in the study of (Nukka, 1998) is seen as an opening entrance or partnership to education fulfillment. Literacy is foundation upon which educational system of a society is built. No one can be educated except he or she overcome the barriers of illiteracy. In the understanding of Graff (2014), he asserted that the epistemology of consideration about literacy are for the most part, evolutionary ones, this implies that the development of literacy must be connected with the development of a society and structure of power and control. Consequently, Ryan (1989) sees literacy as the degree to which an individual possesses mastery over symbols in their written form, or is able to encode or decode the symbols which may be letters or numbers.

Development is the master word the 21st Century. It has pre-occupied writers, Reporters, Analysts, Planners, Organizers, Educators, Trainers, and Policy implementers in all societies. Igbo (2016) sees development as growth, progress and improvement that is all embracing. It refers to an upward ascending movement that features increased level of energy, efficiency, quality, productivity, complexity, creativity, and accomplishment. Development is a progress of social not merely a set of policies and programmes that are initiated for some specific results (UN, 2008).

Adult Education before and after Independence in Nigeria

Adult Education is conceptualized as an educational activity relatively planned and purposefully organized for people, irrespective of their age, location and socio-economic background, those who desire to learn in order to cope more satisfyingly with real life problems (Nyerere, 2006 and Egunyomi, 2015). United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO (1976), further defines it as the entire body of organized educational process whatever the content, level and method, whether formal, or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, colleges and Universities as well as in apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adults in the society to which they belong develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical or professional qualifications and

bring about changes in their attitudes or behaviour in the two fold perspective of full personal development and participation in balanced and independent social, economic and cultural development. Adult and non-formal education covers a variety of activities. It enhances peace, security of lives, civic participation, creativity, innovativeness, novelty, survival of the people and sustainable development.

Promotion of Adult Education in Nigeria pre-dated independence. In fact, it was the advent of missionary to the country that brought about literacy. Aderinoye (1997) reported that the early Christian Missionaries who came to the southern part of Nigeria organized literacy classes for adults who would later serve as interpreters for them, for they perceived that they cannot succeed in their Evangelization bid in Africa without local interpreters who would pass across their messages to the heathen Africans. In the northern part of the country, Qur'an was introduced in many Arabic schools where memorization of verses was encouraged and Islamic religious values and Islamic laws were taught (Osuji, nd). By 1942, in 1942, Mr. Cameron who was the Mass Education Officer had started the Jos Local evening school while Mr. E.R. Chadwick started experimenting in the community development coupled with literacy at Udi. The Udi campaign turned out hundreds of men and women literate in Igbo and some in English (Agbionu, 2014). In 1944, a document titled, Mass Education in African Societies, was issued out by the British colonial government.

In 1946, the first Mass literacy campaign was initiated but failed because of lack of real political will on the part of the Nigerian government. Another document titled, Education for citizenship in Africa was published in 1948. This document suggested the use of village study and discussion groups as well as mass media for the education of the masses. All these documents produced significant changes in the direction of adult education in Nigeria. Macpherson's constitution of 1951 was another factor that helped the development of adult education in Nigeria. The constitution provided for regional governments which had legislative powers over Education, Health etc, hence these Regional Governments initiated policies that geared towards the development of education in general and adult education in particular (Igbo, 2008).

The first comprehensive National Mass Literacy Campaign was launched in 1982 and later reviewed in 1987. The review of the campaign led to the blueprint and National Action Plan for the eradication of literacy in the country. By 1971, various organisations like Non-Governmental Organisations had sprung up. One of them is the NNCAE. By 1976, the Federal Government of Nigeria launched the Universal Primary Education (UPE) Scheme. The UPE was renamed Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999. In 1990, NMEC was established at the federal and state levels. Various donors like UNDP, UNICEF, UNFPA, WHO USAID, UNIDO and European Union are keenly interested in their support to Nigeria on literacy development. Apart from the fact that international donor, voluntary organisations, individuals and so on wake up to challenge illiteracy in Nigeria, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) like NNCAE and NOGALSS presence were prominent.

Non-Governmental Association for Literacy Support Service (NOGALSS)

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) are service bodies that have been in existence before and after the creation of Nigeria (Biao & Adesina, 2006). These NGOs provide both emergency and enduring solutions to economic, Political and Social Problems existing in Nigeria. Recent developments of the national NGOs include NOGALSS. The Non-Governmental Association for Literacy Support Services (NOLGASS) which is an umbrella body for Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) supporting literacy delivery in Nigeria has the mission of all

round literacy and development for all the people of the nation especially, at the grassroots level. It upholds the Right Based Approach of Education for All (EFA). The service of NOLGASS both as an Non-Governmental Organizations NGO and a Civil Society Organization (CSO) include, literacy delivery, Lobbying Agencies, Departments, National and State members. They share information and mobilize for campaign (Biao & Adesina, 2006).

The Objectives of NOGALSS

NOGALSS Constitution (2018) categorized the following are the objectives of the association;

1. Establishing State and Local Government Branches for the purpose of reaching the grassroots.
2. Coordinating the activities of all NGOs and Private Voluntary Organizations (PVOs) involved in delivery of mass literacy.
3. Collaborate with National and International Agencies to facilitate institutional and capacity building of member organization
4. Complementing government efforts in the provision of functional mass literacy and basic education nation-wide.
5. Assisting the country to achieve its targeted literacy level and thus rank among the highly literate nations in the world.
6. Providing a forum for collaboration between Non-Government Organization NGOs, Private Voluntary Organizations PVOs, National and International \Agencies, Federal, State and Local governments in the implementation of literacy programmes.
7. Identifying and maintaining a directory of all relevant Non-Government Organization NGOs and PVOs (Private Voluntary Organizations).

Contribution of Non-Governmental Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) in Adult Literacy and Non-Formal Education

Non-governmental Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) was established in 1993 by national mass education commission, Abuja as an umbrella body for all NGOs, Private Voluntary Organizations (PVOs) and individuals that are involved in mass literacy delivery in Nigeria. It was established to complement government's efforts in the provision of functional mass literacy and basic education at all levels. NOGALSS was set up by NGOs that are fully or partly working on adult literacy and non-formal education sub-sector government efforts in the delivery of adult literacy programmes in Nigeria. NOGALSS collaborate with Ministries Department and Agencies (MDAS) such as National Commission for Mass Literacy, Adult and Non-Formal Education (NMEC) and State Agencies for Mass Education (SAMEs), development partners such as UNICEF, UNESCO, ACTION AID and other NGOs like Civil Society Action Coalition on Education for All (CSACEFA) and Nigeria National Council for Adult Education (NNCAE) to fight the menace of illiteracy in the country. Vision and Mission: The association was set up to help in the eradication of illiteracy in Nigeria where over 65 million peoples are believed to be non-literate, among them women, children and youths. Its vision is to see a society where the citizenry can read and write in at least two languages. The mother tongue and English which the official language of the country, with the view of accessing and utilizing information beneficial for their general well-being. Its mission is to assist the country to achieve its target literacy level through effective coordination of relevant Civil Society Organization (CSOs) advocacy, community sensitization and partnership and establishment of literacy centers and empowerment programmes. Members of this association learn from each other and contribute, in one way or the other, in uplifting adult literacy education forward by pooling their resources

together to set up literacy centres and train literacy workers such as facilitators, organizers, supervisors, among others to run the programmes (additional information from the current) (NOGALSS President, 2008).

At present NOGALSS is collaborating with NMEC on its rural facilitation scheme in all the 36 state country. Here, members volunteer to teach in literacy centers across the state with training and some materials support from NMEC. Both NNCAE and NOGALSS are contributing effectively in complimenting the efforts of the various tiers of government and development partners in advancing the course of adult and non-formal education in the country. Kogi NOGALSS was set up with a vision of ensuring Education for All (EFA) by 2030, with a mission of achieving the vision target through effective advocacy, community sensitization, collaborations and establishment of literacy centres and organizing empowerment programmes for our learners. (NOGALSS, 2018).

Kogi State NOGALSS has structures at zonal and local government levels and are represented in every ward. The programmes being supported by the umbrella NGO include basic literacy, post literacy, nomadic education, adult junior secondary schools, skill acquisition and empowerment programmes. The target audience includes unschooled children, youths and adults who had no or abdicated the privilege of going to formal school and women. Its success is as a result of the combined efforts of all people drawn from all professions and organizations. This includes the support receive from the office of senior special education agency, traditional rulers, faith-based organizations and individuals helping in the area of community sensitization and mobilization.

Since the inception of NOGALSS in Kogi State, about 1500 people were made literacy. Many of whom are presently in secondary school; vocational education centres with many others doing well in their respective businesses while others are gainfully employed. At present one 4000 learners are enrolled in basic and post literacy programmes across the state (NOGALSS, 2018).

Concept of Literacy

The concept of literacy has been defined differently based on their development and needs of a specific community (Oni, 2017; Amadi & Uchechi, 2018). The following are some of the concepts: Literacy can be defined as the ability of an individual person to understand and make use of printed information in daily activities - at home, at work and in the community, and to achieve one's goals and develop one's knowledge and potential (Alvermann, et.al. 2018). In relation to work, literacy can also refer to the essential skills that enable people to be effective in performing the tasks required by their job/occupation and/or desired job/occupation (Ladeji&Okoji, 2014; Nagele, &Stalder, 2017).

Literacy does not only enable people to learn, it equally provides a base and foundation for learning other necessary skills, and helps in enhancing the people's ability to be creative, innovative and adapt to economical dynamic change. Some of the skills include but not limited to reading, writing, basic numeracy, effective oral communication, interpersonal relationship, logical and critical thinking, use of computer, as well as continuous learning (Mbah.2015). The primary sense of literacy still represents lifelong, intellectual process of gaining meaning from a critical interpretation of the written or printed text (Adelore&Olumukoro, 2015). The key to all literacy is reading development a progression of skills that begins with the ability to understand spoken words and decode written words and culminates in the deep understanding of text (Omole&Ozaji, 2014). According to the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2019), literacy is critical for

promoting and communicating sustainable development and improving the capacity of people to address environment and development issues. It facilitates the achievement of environmental and ethical awareness, values, and skills consistent with sustainable development and effective public participation in decision making.

The National Commission for Mass Literacy, Adult and non-formal Education (NMEC, 2017) Policy Guidelines for Mass Literacy, Adult and Non-Formal Education stipulated an outlined effective system and strategies which are intended to support the operation of adult and non-formal education programmes and institutions in Nigeria. The literacy programme is targeted at adults and adolescents who has never been to school and cannot read or write and for whom basic literacy and numeracy skills can open a gate to lifelong learning; adults and adolescents who are above school-going age but have not achieved reading, writing and numeracy competencies (NMEC, 2017).

The Global Monitoring Report (2006) affirms that literacy is a "contextually bound continuum of reading, writing and numeracy developed through the learning and application in school and in other settings appropriate to youths and adult, similarly, the new UNESCO (2014) definition of literacy defined it as the ability to read, write and to work on simple arithmetic and also to acquire skills in the use of computer, so that the individual can function effectively in the society.

Literacy Education

Literacy education has a special role in the process of community development and growth. This is because education service serves as a vehicle that set up other economic process into motion, Biallo (2002), he stressed further that, an educated and literate society serve as a pivot or better still an orbit upon which the development of the kinds resolves. The acquisitions of literacy avails the recipient the opportunity for personal development and enable him or her to become a matured and responsible citizen to his country. According to Faley, (2002), the major inhibition to community and societal structural development is the prevalence of both in the rural areas and urban fringes Illiteracy as been regarded as an energy which keeps people permanently in the darkness to their tradition and superstition which need to be changed, most especially now that the world as become a global village.

Literacy in the study of (Nukka, 1998) is seen as an opening entrance or partway to education fulfillment. Literacy is foundation upon which educational system of a society is built. No one can be educated except he or she overcome the barriers of illiteracy. In the understanding of Graff (2014), he asserted that the epistemology of consideration about literacy is for the most part, evolutionary ones, this implies that the development of literacy must be connected with the development of a society and structure of power and control. Consequently, Ryan (1989) sees literacy as the degree to which an individual possesses mastery over symbols in their written form, or is able to encode or decode the symbols which may be letters or numbers. In the same vain; (UNESCO, 2015), sees literacy in the line of culture and nationality. That literacy is the ability to read and write in mother tongue. This implies that literacy in one language of country may not be considered so in another country.

Therefore, a person literate in Spanish may be seen as an illiterate where English or French languages are used. However, regardless of the language a person can use to express himself, the most important thing is to be literate. This is because literacy helps man to understand his environment and precautions be taken to survive in the dynamic world.

Types of Literacy Programmes

United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO (1981) categorized literacy into traditional, cultural, civic, women and functional types. Traditional literacy, according to the United Nations Organization, is that type of literacy which entails the teaching of reading and writing, accompanied by elementary Arithmetic (Aderinoye, 2004). Cultural literacy entails active enjoyment of culture and active participation in the cultural activities of the society. This type of literacy according to Paulo Freire (2019) entails the continuous rebirth of indigenous culture in the lives of the people. Ultimately, cultural literacy is expected to bring about critical literacy.

Civic literacy is literacy for citizenship and the focus of which is to enlighten the populace about their duties and responsibilities as well as their rights. Women literacy is the type of literacy given to the women folk in order to empower them as well as sensitize them on their rights and duties as beneficiaries and citizens. According to United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO functional literacy is tied to economic functions and which are based on the psychology of an adult at work. The focus of this type of literacy is to integrate reading, writing and numeracy with economic skills for sustainable livelihood.

Literacy can also be graded according to different programme levels as well. For instance, there is basic literacy, post-literacy, continuing and remedial education. Literacy can also be classified according to its mode of delivery such as visual, print, social, scientific, political, critical work place and computer literacy. There is also literacy in languages, literacy for schooling, the home, market, work place, family and spiritual work (Obi, in Usman,2008). NMEC (2017) categorized literacy into eight categories viz:

- a. **Basic Literacy:** This is equivalent to primary 1 to 3 of the formal system. It is designed to provide reading, writing, numeracy and skills for adults and youths who did not have an opportunity for formal education.
- b. **Post Literacy:** This is equivalent to primary 4 to 6 of the formal education system. It is part of the NFE organized for graduates of basic literacy who want to acquire more knowledge and for those one who, for one reason or the other, dropped-out from formal school between primary 1 -3. The concept of post-literacy assumes that newly literates quickly relapse into illiteracy if they do not have any meaningful ways of using their skills. The post-literacy stage usually lasts for 2 -3 years. From this level, a learner can proceed for further education either through the formal or open and distance learning system.
- c. **Advance Literacy:** As the name indicates, learners that have passed through both basic and post literacy are grouped under advance class. This category of learners has got to the level of registering for primary school certificate and can cope well in the junior secondary I and II. In fact, advanced learners are been exposed to subjects like Mathematics, Science subjects, English and Civic education.
- d. **Functional Literacy:** This form of literacy is "work-related" and is mainly intended to promote literacy through the familiar objects and acts of the learners' professional or vocational calling. That is, providing the skills of reading, writing and computation tailored towards one's occupation for better economic productivity.
- e. **Vocational Education/Work-related Skills:** This is a non-formal education programme designed to equip learners with vocational or work-related skills such as livelihood, computational skills, work readiness, entrepreneurial and small business management.
- f. **Liberal Education:** This is a type of education designed to enlighten the learners (or people) on health (e.g., illness and diseases prevention) environment (e.g conservation, protection),

civic (e.g participating in democratic process such as election), peace education, conflict resolution, parenting (including specific programmes for mothers), psycho-social well-being, negotiating and assertive skills.

- g. **Continuing Education:** This is a form of literacy that is designed to prepare the learner for returning to formal school or to pass examinations. It is an educational programme organized for graduates of post-literacy and non-completers of the formal school, especially those who want to acquire Junior School Certificate Examination (JSCE), Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE), including professional examinations or other external examinations of their choice or individuals who want to remedy deficiencies in their educational pursuit. This type of education assumes the forms of Remedial Education, Extra-Mural and Open & Distance Learning.
- h. **Workplace Basic Skills:** This is mostly provided by public or private sector employers. It is arranged for the non-literate and moderately literate employees to spend some work-time learning how to read, write and calculate or to update their skills, both for the purposes of their work and possible promotion and for more general education.

According Onuoha and Nwosu (2013), some of the major importance of adult literacy education include but not limited to the following:

1. **Ensure a productive future:** Adult literacy promises a good future as it provides a good character to a person. It enables one to make best use of one's skills and talent and help in fetching the most competitive jobs. Importance of continuing education can be realized in the height achieved by great and famous personalities in different fields of education.
2. **Opens New Vistas:** The magnitude of education lies in its ability to broaden the mental scope and open new vistas that are inaccessible otherwise. It enables one to understand different dimensions of a particular point-of-view, which an uneducated person cannot. It helps in making a person tolerant and humble, and at the same time removes the darkness of ignorance. This is the ultimate goal of education.
3. **Helps in Decision-making:** Education broadens the framework of the mind and enables us to take the right decisions at right times. In every sphere of life, we are supposed to take right decisions that might be very wrong and thereby preventing grave losses.
4. **Bolsters Confidence:** Self-brief is the most important trait in making a good human being and education helps in augmenting the self-confidence, fostering positive outlook and allowing us to rely on ourselves.
5. **Spreads Awareness:** Education spreads awareness about right and wrong. It informs us about our rights and the services we can access; at the same time emphasizing on the duties entrusted upon us by the society.
6. **Makes Better Citizens:** Education that opens our mind and expands our horizons, which plays a crucial role in shaping us to be good and responsible citizens. Education helps us to learn about our culture and our history, and subsequently imbibe those values to become better (Madu&Obiozor, 2015).

Literacy has also been found to be important in the social, political, and ideological contexts. Spark (2002), for example, related literacy to identity, arguing that literacy develops as one masters the communication processes, the symbolic media, the cultural norms, values, and beliefs of a particular community. Rather than execute a prescribed set of tasks to perform a particular social role, the socio-cultural model understands literacy as constituted through particular practices so that individuals construct their identities based on their acculturation and

participation within socio-cultural communities (Mercieca, 2014). From this perspective, understanding spoken or written communication, involves knowing who is reading and who is authoring as well as the context and purpose of communication (Nkunguu, 2014).

Benefits of Adult Literacy Programmes in Nigeria

The benefits of Adult literacy Programmes are so numerous that it is widely believed to be capable of enhancing sustainable development. Alkali (2008) has enumerated the various uses and benefits of literacy as follows:

- i. It encourages citizens participation in government policies and programmes
- ii. It aids memory and sense of reasoning
- iii. It assists in documentation and easy record keeping
- iv. It helps in verification and stimulates thinking
- v. It aids invention and innovations and helps in transmission of ideals, values and commitment
- vi. It makes one independent and allows for cooperation and a sense of togetherness
- vii. It helps adults to have access to information and the development of critical awareness

United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization UNESCO (2014) has also landed some support to the issue of usefulness and benefits of literacy, when it enumerated additional uses of literacy as follows.

- i. It helps learners to get knowledge and skills that are useful in everyday life activities,
- ii. it helps learners to communicate to people, especially in writing,
- iii. it gives the learner a feeling of self-confidence,
- iv. personal security and freedom from being cheated or exploited,
- v. it helps the individual to actively participate in politics,
- vi. it increases ones economic, political and social gains,
- vii. it helps the individual to operate new machines (such as the ATM)

From the submissions above it is clear that the uses and benefits of literacy are so numerous that it is capable of playing a great role in achieving development. UNESCO, 2014

Objectives of Adult Literacy Programmes

Adult Literacy Education is a type of education in Nigeria meant to make education accessible to various learners who have no access to it at the early age of their life. The objectives of mass literacy, adult and non-formal education as spelt out in the National Policy on Education (2004) is to:

- i. Provide functional literacy education for adults who have never had the advantage of any formal education.
- ii. Provide functional and remedial education for those young people who prematurely dropped out of the formal school system.
- iii. Provide further education for different categories of completers of the formal education system in order to improve their basic knowledge and skills.
- iv. Provide in-service, on-the-job, vocational and professional training for different categories of workers and professionals in order to improve their skill.
- v. Give the adult citizens of the country necessary aesthetic, cultural and civic education for public enlightenment.

The above are the objectives of adult and continuing education of which functional literacy education is inclusive. However, the objectives are well framed but one problem of Nigeria is that,

there is always good policy but poor implementation. Observation revealed that the objectives stated are yet to be achieved fully.

Literacy and Development

Literacy is an integral part of basic education and the benefit of quality basic education to individuals and the society is immense. A good basic education strengthened by the acquisition of literacy and numeracy is the minimum educational foundation upon which an individual can build lifelong learning attitudes. This is the reason why from as far back as the 70s, the federal government had started to emphasize functional literacy in all its policy documents the national policy on education in 1977 to date: the decree establishing the national commission for mass literacy, adult and non-formal education decree 17 of 1990; the vision 20; 2020 and the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy [NEEDS'2004] to mention a few. Empowered by literacy and numeracy, a person will be able to recognize and make economic, social and political choices.

It is recognized by the government that literacy education will help equip individual with the knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for economic self-sufficiency, poverty reduction and sustainable development. Adult literacy will help the people to ease challenges of poverty, income generation, health issues, shelter, food, security etc. However this is still a huge challenge as the majority of illiterates in Nigeria live in remote rural communities, far from the purview of the government. They remain marginalized and unreachable.

Development is the master word of the 21st Century. It has preoccupied writers, reporters, analysts, planners, organizers, educators, trainers, and policy implementers in all societies. Igbo (2016) sees development as growth, progress and improvement that is all embracing. It refers to an upward ascending movement that features increased level of energy, efficiency, quality, productivity, complexity, creativity and accomplishment. Development is a process of social not merely a set of policies and programme that are initiated for some specific results (UN, 2008). Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary sees it as the "gradual growth of something so that it becomes more advanced and stronger". Since development can be said to be making the gains and advancement more permanent and lasting. In other words, development would mean that all the gains and advancement in life achieved through the various means including literacy, be it economic, social, political, educational, religious or spiritual should be permanent and lasting in nature.

More so, most people would agree, is a term with a positive connotation; that is, development is associated with a better future. However, whether a given change is regarded as good or bad involves value judgments over which it is often difficult to come to agreement. This is not the least because what we consider good or bad changes over time and is subject to different interpretations according to differences in perspectives. Traditionally, economists have measured development in terms of increasing per capital income or gross domestic product. But the distribution of income is skewed and the poor part of the population is getting poorer even while average income increases, many people - including many economists would hesitate to call this development. The UN Development Programme (1994) defines development as processes that increase people's opportunity of choice. Ecologists, on their part, would tend to regard processes that threaten environmental robustness as negative even if they benefit people.

Others would highlight the state of education and health in the society as important factors in meeting basic needs. Education creates knowledge, skills and capabilities allowing greater individual choice and freedom and, as such is an important part of development. Finally,

institutional freedom and choice and are, according to some, essential parameters by which the level of development should be judged. What these entire ideas share in common is a focus on making humans better off in one way or another. Therefore, for the purposes of this study, development will be thought of as an increase in well-being across the members of a society between two points in time.

The above scenario show that the word development means different things to different people, but according to Ariyo (2006) in Olojede (2011), it is generally composed of four elements: Political; Economic; Social and Cultural. The level of political development is measured, to a large extent, by the degree of openness of the political system that ensures equal opportunity for every eligible citizen to aspire and be elected into any public office of his/her choice, as well as strong societal institutions that promote good political governance. The ultimate here is to entrench political democracy. Social development, which is characterized by harmonious relations among the populace, is equally facilitated through the provision of the right type, quantity and quality of basic needs and social services, such as education and health, and equity in the allocation of services, benefits and obligations. Closely related to this according to Ariyo (2006), is cultural development, whereby a society gradually graduates from the so-called society to a modern society, without loss of its distinct cultural identity. This is achievable through incremental adjustments to the ethics, values and ways of life of the people in a manner that promotes good societal relationships.

Development is thus about expanding the choices people have to lead lives they value. And it is thus much more than economic growth, which is only a means — if a very important one — of enlarging people's choices. Fundamental to enlarging these choices is building human capabilities- the range of things that people can do or be in life. The most basic capabilities for human development are to lead a long and healthy life, to be knowledgeable, to have access to the resources needed for a decent standard of living, and to be able to participate in the life of the community. Without these, many choices are simply not available, and many opportunities in life remain inaccessible (UNDP, 2001).

Conclusion

Literacy for All is the concern for all stakeholders in Education and Adult Education in particular, in Nigeria. It is obvious that the government has demonstrated its willingness to remedy the situation but the stark reality is that the current strides are short for the distance to be covered. It is still in our hands as stakeholders to continue to rise up to the challenges to make Nigerians literate and to achieve our goal of reducing illiteracy. It was established in this study that Adult Education has potentials inherent in Literacy Education that could assist in reducing inequality, unemployment and underemployment which are resulted in weak democracy instability of government, Poverty, Crime and Conflict of which of which women are the vulnerable in Nigeria. This also provides a conceptual framework for institutional analysis, linking the elements of the action Literacy Education, Non-Governmental Association for Literacy Support Services (NOGALSS) situation of Literacy development in Nigeria, types of Literacy programme in Nigeria.

The growth of economies of nation is due to increasing participation and involvement of Literacy development activities as listed above. In their own way of informal way, literacy programmes have been manufactures and industrialists, productive. Contributions to the development and the society, Non-Governmental Association for Literacy Support Services

(NOGALSS) should as a matter of urgency assist improving the lot of women by sensitizing and educating the people on the need for literacy stem. Unemployment, underemployment.

Recommendations

1. Identification of literacy centers is not enough; quality assurance should be maintained through effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms such as literacy monitoring officers and standardized test as evaluation mechanisms
2. Awareness of programmes among all stakeholders for the promotion of literacy in Nigeria should be a continuous project. The operation and implementation should also incorporate those who are specialists or who specialize in adult education and adult literacy for efficiency.
3. Awareness programmes among all stakeholders for the promotion of literacy in Nigeria should be a continuous project. The operation and implementation should also incorporate those who are specialists or who specialize in adult education and adult literacy for efficiency.
4. Identification of literacy centers ins not enough, quality assurance should be maintained through effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms such as literacy monitoring officers and standardized test as evaluation mechanisms.
5. Planning and disbursement of fund should consider specific target group per session. A clear definition of this group will help in the incorporation and budgetary allocation of such group e.g. if 'Youth Corpers' will be used as suggested, as facilitators, then they should be fixed appropriately in the budget yearly so that they are paid as at when due to avoid loss of interest and abandonment or discontinuity.

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